

Table 4. Reasons for referrals provided by psychologists and AHPs/clinicians

Reason for referral	Psychologists	AHPs/Clinicians
	N=34 N (%)	N=130 N (%)
Anxiety	31 (91.2)	126 (96.2)
Parenting (adjustment and coping)	23 (67.6)	71 (54.2)
Patient adjustment	22 (64.7)	72 (55.0)
Coping with symptoms/symptoms exacerbated by stress or anxiety	22 (64.7)	111 (84.7)
Food challenges	18 (52.9)	81 (61.8)
Acute/traumatic stress	16 (47.1)	89 (67.9)
Needle phobia	16 (47.1)	70 (53.4)
Adherence (dietary or medical)	16 (47.1)	69 (52.7)
Mood	15 (44.1)	63 (48.1)
Support with new diagnosis	14 (41.2)	66 (50.4)
Parenting (behavioural management)	12 (35.3)	42 (32.1)
Self-esteem	9 (26.5)	62 (47.3)
Body image	7 (20.6)	53 (40.5)
Anger	5 (14.7)	50 (38.2)
Bullying	4 (11.8)	54 (41.2)
Social isolation	3 (8.8)	62 (47.3)